

1 **Metabolic changes associated with endotoxin (LPS) tolerance in human monocytes and**
2 **macrophage.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We recently discovered and described a suite of nuclear factors that function in tolerized transcriptional
8 responses to lipopolysaccharide (endotoxin) which included Sp family transcriptome factors and
9 epigenetic factors of the TDRD and JMJD family. Tolerized responses to bacterial products are an
10 important regulatory mechanism which shapes, sustains and restrains control of pathogens by the innate
11 immune system is accompanied by significant changes in transcription, metabolism, and epigenetic
12 modulation of the host genome. We measured total transcription in human cells following a “trained”,
13 secondary response to endotoxin resulting from a previous primary exposure to the ligand. We observed
14 significant changes in expression of genes functioning in metabolism. The range of genes with functions
15 in cellular metabolism whose expression was influenced by endotoxin tolerance included ME3, FBP1,
16 ND3, and FMO5. Trained responses to bacterial products, tolerance to endotoxin, is both executed
17 through combinatorial assembly of nuclear factors that titrate the rapid innate immune response and
18 characterized by important changes in the metabolic profile of the immune cell.

19 **References**

20 1. Tannahill, G.M., Curtis, A.M., Adamik, J., Palsson-McDermott, E.M., McGettrick, A.F., Goel, G.,
21 Frezza, C., Bernard, N.J., Kelly, B., Foley, N.H. and Zheng, L., 2013. Succinate is an inflammatory signal
22 that induces IL-1 β through HIF-1 α . *Nature*, 496(7444), pp.238-242.

23 2. Mills, E.L., Kelly, B., Logan, A., Costa, A.S., Varma, M., Bryant, C.E., Tourlomousis, P., Däbritz,
24 J.H.M., Gottlieb, E., Latorre, I. and Corr, S.C., 2016. Succinate dehydrogenase supports metabolic
25 repurposing of mitochondria to drive inflammatory macrophages. *Cell*, 167(2), pp.457-470.

26 3. Palsson-McDermott, E.M., Curtis, A.M., Goel, G., Lauterbach, M.A., Sheedy, F.J., Gleeson, L.E.,
27 van den Bosch, M.W., Quinn, S.R., Domingo-Fernandez, R., Johnston, D.G. and Jiang, J.K., 2015.
28 Pyruvate kinase M2 regulates Hif-1 α activity and IL-1 β induction and is a critical determinant of the
warburg effect in LPS-activated macrophages. *Cell metabolism*, 21(1), pp.65-80.

4. Hoofman, A., Peace, C.G., Ryan, D.G., Day, E.A., Yang, M., McGettrick, A.F., Yin, M., Montano,
E.N., Huo, L., Toller-Kawahisa, J.E. and Zecchini, V., 2023. Macrophage fumarate hydratase restrains
mtRNA-mediated interferon production. *Nature*, 615(7952), pp.490-498.

5. Seim, G.L., Britt, E.C., John, S.V., Yeo, F.J., Johnson, A.R., Eisenstein, R.S., Pagliarini, D.J. and
Fan, J., 2019. Two-stage metabolic remodelling in macrophages in response to lipopolysaccharide and
interferon- γ stimulation. *Nature metabolism*, 1(7), pp.731-742.